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Disturbance-Learning Predictive Control of the Ground Station of an Airborne Wind Energy System

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The field of automatic control for Airborne Wind Energy Systems (AWES) is in continuous development [1]. In particular, flight control design and optimization have been extensively addressed in the last years [2].

This work is focused on the development of an efficient control strategy for the ground station of an AWES, which is crucial for ensuring an effective and safe operation of the whole system. Moreover, an efficient winch control strategy helps preventing excessive wear and tear of the system's components.

To this end, a novel Model Predictive Control (MPC) formulation is presented, aimed at exploring the integration of periodic disturbances rejection techniques into the MPC framework. The issue of compensating for periodic disturbances in dynamical systems is still open, especially when a model of the disturbance is not available. In this simulation-based application, the goal is to track the reference speed given by the flight dynamics, while compensating for disturbances on the tether load, possibly deriving from sources such as turbulence or, in a hypothetical off-shore context, wave motion.

The approach is to learn the periodic component of the disturbance by means of real-time measurements and predictions, then exploit this model to recursively update the prediction model of the MPC at any step of the optimization process. Key performance metrics, including disturbance rejection amplitude, control effort and tracking accuracy have been used to assess the effectiveness of the proposed approach. Besides, a comparison with traditional offset-free-based MPC has been performed to show the enhancement of the control performance.

Ground station control simulation result: tether reeling speed reference tracking in pumping operation using disturbance learning model predictive control.

References:

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